

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1. List of Level 0 plasmids generated and expression vectors used during this work. All sequences can be searched at <https://gbcloning.upv.es/search/features/> using the GB ID.

Name	GB ID
pUPD2 CR3009	<u>GB3576</u>
pUPD2 CR3018	<u>GB3575</u>
pUPD2 CR3022	<u>GB3577</u>
pUPD2 Sybody3	<u>GB3402</u>
pUPD2 Sybody17	<u>GB3403</u>
pUPD2 Nanobody72	<u>GB3404</u>
pUPD2 natRBD:His	<u>GB3377</u>
pUPD2 bcoRBD:His	<u>GB3382</u>
pUPD2 His:natRBD:KDEL	<u>GB3441</u>
pUPD2 His:bcoRBD:KDEL	<u>GB3442</u>
pUPD2 His:bcoN	<u>GB3447</u>
pGreen SP-hIgG1	<u>GB3604</u>
pCambiaV1	<u>GB1373</u>
pCambiaV2	<u>GB3603</u>